

A Novel Method in Membrane Separation Processes : Electroosmotic Separation of Liquid Mixtures^ψ

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A novel technique in membrane separation based on the phenomenon of electroosmosis, recently developed by the author, has been used to demonstrate the practicability of the phenomenon for separation of azeotropic liquid mixtures. The method shows favourable prospects in membrane separation processes. The analysis of the data indicates that the separation of benzene in ethanol-benzene mixture and dioxane in dioxane-water mixture increases with increase in temperature. Further, the separation increases with increase in applied electrical potential difference.

The existing methods, such as, reverse osmosis, ultrafiltration, electro dialysis, pervaporation and coupled membrane transport with positive improvements have acquired important role in membrane separation processes¹⁻³. These methods have been applied to a range of diverse applications¹⁻⁵. Meanwhile, liquid membrane technology has emerged as a subset of membrane separation science³. In some situations, the liquid membranes have proved better alternatives for effective separation, particularly in separation of azeotropic liquid mixtures^{6,7}. Quite recently, the idea of Cohen and Raydt⁸ has been used by us⁹ to develop a new technique in membrane separation, based on the phenomenon of electroosmosis. For the first time, on bench scale experiments, practicability of the technique has been demonstrated for separation of liquid mixtures.

From the membrane separation point of view, the development of new techniques are of utmost importance, since these may serve new tool for studying separation of liquid mixtures and may also have diverse applications in other separation processes. Herein, we report the effect of temperature on the separation of azeotropic liquid mixtures, in addition to our previous studies.

Theory :

The electroosmotic velocity of permeants across a membrane can be expressed as⁹⁻¹²

$$J_v = \frac{\epsilon \xi r^2}{4 \eta l} \Delta\phi \quad (1)$$

where, J_v , r , ξ , ϵ , η , l and $\Delta\phi$ represent volume flow, average pore radius of membrane, zeta potential, dielectric constant of the medium, length of the capillary in the membrane and applied electrical potential difference respectively. Parameter r and l are considered to be fixed for a particular membrane. The quantities ξ , ϵ and η are expected to vary with the nature of permeants. ξ does not vary appreciably with composition of mixture in comparison to ϵ and η ^{9,11,12}. This implies that J_v mainly

depends on dielectric constant and viscosity of the medium. Further, magnitude changes in the value of ϵ with concentration is more pronounced than η ^{9,13}. With all these qualitative assumptions equation (1) can be written in a simpler form,

$$J_v = K' \epsilon \Delta\phi \quad (2)$$

where, K' includes all fix parameters and those which do not change appreciably with composition of the mixture.

Since dielectric constant remains the same for pure components, equation (2) can be expressed as

$$J_v = K \Delta\phi \quad (3)$$

where, $K = K' \epsilon$. Equation (3) predicts a linear plot between J_v and $\Delta\phi$, passing through the origin.

Results and Discussion

The data on electroosmosis (system 1) of set I, set III and set V were plotted against $\Delta\phi$ to test the validity of equation (3). As such equation (3) was not found valid in any set. However, the electroosmotic permeability would be quantitatively represented by equation,

$$J_v = K\Delta\phi + K_1 \Delta\phi^2 + K_3 \Delta\phi^3 + \dots \quad (4)$$

Here K_1 , K_2 etc. are higher order coefficients which can all be derived from the first order coefficient of equation (3). No electroosmosis was observed in set II and set IV (system 1). However, it was observed that during electroosmosis of mixture the benzene molecules were dragged across the membrane with the ethanol molecule to enrich the permeate side. An obvious implication of this observation is that benzene is dragged owing to the large friction with ethanol and very small friction with glass membrane. This can be attributed to another fact : that the structured nature of hydrogen bonded system restricts the freedom of motion and tends to increase viscosity¹⁴. It is therefore expected that ethanol will have greater friction relative to glass membrane than benzene. This is consistent with the explanation presented elsewhere¹⁵.

^ψBased on the lecture delivered in the Symposium on "Interface Science Applications" during the 31st Annual Convention of Chemists held at Varanasi, 1994.

For system 2, the electroosmotic transport data of set I, set III and set V were plotted against $\Delta\phi$. No electroosmosis was observed either in set II or in set IV. Equation (3) was found valid in set I. However in set III and set V, an equation similar to equation (4) was found to be obeyed. An important feature arose in this system when concentration of dioxane increased in the mixture, i.e. when $X_D > 0.1$ in both chambers. A threshold value of $\Delta\phi$ equal to ~ 10 V was obtained, below which no electroosmosis was recorded. The form of the transport equation which represents the data in this situation can be written as

$$J_v = K (\Delta\phi - \Delta\phi_0) + K_1 (\Delta\phi - \Delta\phi_0)^2 + \dots \quad (5)$$

where, $\Delta\phi_0$ is the threshold electrical potential difference below which no electroosmosis takes place.

In the present study, dioxane possesses very low dielectric constant in comparison to water¹³ and hence polarisation of dioxane molecules in presence of electrical potential difference is not possible. This indicates that the electroosmotic velocity of water should be higher in comparison to mixture. This suggests the following trend when both sides were filled with solution of same composition,

$$(J_v)_{\text{water}} > (J_v)_{X_D = 0.1} > (J_v)_{X_D = 0.2} \dots > (J_v)_{\text{dioxane}} \approx 0$$

The above trend was followed with our experimental data.

Degree of separation : To estimate the degree of separation of dioxane, we followed the lines of reverse osmosis in which driving force is essentially the pressure difference and degree of separation is reported either as separation factor or rejection depending on the operating conditions. Since, in the present technique the driving force is electrical potential difference, we prefer to make use of the following relation^{9,6,17}

$$\alpha_{ij} = (P/F)_i / (P/F)_j \quad (6)$$

The physical significance of the separation factor in the present case can be understood as follows. (i) If $\alpha_{ij} = 1$, the component i and j are not separated from the mixture. (ii) If $\alpha_{ij} > 1$, the more permeable component i separates and enrich the permeate side. (iii) If $\alpha_{ij} < 1$, the less permeable component j separates and enrich permeate side. Equation (6) can be written as

$$\text{for system 1 : } \alpha_{AB} = (P/F)_A / (P/F)_B \quad (7)$$

$$\text{and for system 2 : } \alpha_{WD} = (P/F)_W / (P/F)_D \quad (8)$$

In equations (6-8), α is the separation factor, P and F are permeate and feed concentrations, and subscripts A, B, W and D stand for ethanol, benzene, water and dioxane respectively.

The separation factor has been calculated in two different sets of experiments : one in which applied electrical field was varied and the other in which concentration of feed-side was varied. It is worth to mention that after an interval of 30 min the solution in each chamber was analysed to note the change in concentration. The values of separation factor thus estimated are given in Tables 1 and 2 for

system 1 and system 2 respectively. It is obvious from Table 1 that the separation of benzene increases with increase of applied electrical potential difference across the membrane. However, the separation of benzene increases with decrease of benzene concentration in the feed solution.

TABLE 1—DEGREE OF SEPARATION IN SYSTEM 1 : ETHANOL AND BENZENE MIXTURE AT 30°

Initial conc in both sides of membrane 0.2 mole fraction of benzene in ethanol ($X_B = 0.2$)		Applied $\Delta\phi = 50$ V and initial conc. permeate side 0.2 mole fraction of benzene in ethanol ($X_B = 0.2$)	
$\Delta\phi$ V	$\alpha_{AB} \times 10^2$	Feed-side concn. X_B	$\alpha_{AB} \times 10^2$
10	98.36	0.200	87.40
20	95.40	0.184	86.10
30	93.68	0.166	81.20
40	89.32	0.140	74.60
50	87.80	0.136	67.90
60	85.10		
70	79.72		
80	74.25		
90	68.22		

TABLE 2—DEGREE OF SEPARATION IN SYSTEM 2 : WATER AND DIOXANE MIXTURE AT 30°

Initial conc. in both compartments $X_D = 0.1$		Applied $\Delta\phi = 50$ V and initial conc. in permeate chamber $X_D = 0.1$	
$\Delta\phi$	$\alpha_{WD} \times 10^2$	Feed-side concn. X_D	$\alpha_{WD} \times 10^2$
5	101.34	0.01	10.73
10	103.27	0.05	54.06
20	105.94	0.10	114.76
30	107.88	0.15	151.60
40	109.70	0.20	187.50
50	114.94		
60	120.52		
70	124.22		
80	132.98		
90	138.60		
100	147.58		

From Table 2 it can be seen that the separation of dioxane increases with increase of $\Delta\phi$. Contrary to the findings in system 1, the separation of dioxane increases with increase of dioxane concentration in the feed chamber. This can be rationalised in terms of the fact that the dielectric constant of the medium decreases with increase of dioxane concentration, and since $\Delta\phi$ is applied from feed to permeate side, dioxane concentrates in feed chamber and water passes in permeate chamber.

Effect of temperature on separation factor : Variations in temperature have a great many largely interrelated effects upon membrane separation processes. In addition to the increased motion of the solvent and solute molecules

and decreasing interactions between the two, membrane-solvent and membrane-solute interactions are also affected. While studying the temperature effect on the separation factor, the other two parameters, i.e. the applied electrical potential difference and feed-side and permeate-side concentration were fixed. The data thus obtained are recorded in Table 3 for systems 1 and 2. The results reveal that the degree of separation in system 1 decreases and in system 2 increases with increase in temperature.

TABLE 3—TEMPERATURE DEPENDENCE OF DEGREE OF SEPARATION

System 1		System 2	
Initial concn. in both compartments $X_B = 0.2$ and applied $\Delta\phi = 50$ V		Initial concn. in both compartments $X_D = 0.1$ and applied $\Delta\phi = 50$ V	
T	α_{AB}	T	α_{WD}
K	$\times 10^2$	K	$\times 10^2$
293	95.14	293	108.44
298	90.26	298	110.23
303	87.84	303	114.94
308	86.02	308	120.21
313	85.14	313	125.71

The temperature dependence of separation factor can be expressed as Arrhenius relationship,

$$\alpha_{ij} = (\alpha_{ij})_{T_0} e^{-E_a/RT} \tag{9}$$

where, α_{ij} is the separation factor, $(\alpha_{ij})_{T_0}$ the separation factor at lowest temperature (20° in the present case), E_a the activation energy, R the universal gas constant and T the absolute temperature. Equation (9) predicts a straight-line between $\log \alpha_{ij}$ and $1/T$ plot with an intercept at

Fig. 1 Separation factor as a function of temperature.

$(\alpha_{ij})_{T_0}$. It can be seen from Fig. 1 that equation (9) is not valid throughout the range of temperatures. Alternatively, $[\log \alpha_{ij} - \log (\alpha_{ij})_{T_0}]$ has been plotted against $1/T$ (Fig. 2).

From Fig. 2 it can be concluded that the validity of equation (9) in system 1 is upto 30° and in system 2 upto 35° . In system 1, the retardation of separation factor started above 30° . This can be understood in view of the fact that viscosity of the medium decreases as the temperature increases [cf. eqn. (1)]. Furthermore, the interactions between ethanol and benzene become weak. This implies that the number of molecules of benzene dragged with ethanol molecules should be comparatively less at high temperature.

Fig. 2. Plot of $[\log (\alpha_{ij}) - \log (\alpha_{ij})_{T_0}]$ against $1/T$ · (o) system 1 (ethanol-benzene) and (•) system 2 (water-dioxane).

The water and dioxane make very weak interactions in mixture. These interactions would be further weakened at high temperature. Moreover, in system 2, only water molecules passes across the membrane and viscosity of water tends to decrease with increase in temperature. Hence, separation is more favourable at high temperature as can be seen from Fig. 2. It has been hinted¹ that the effect of temperature on membrane separations of aqueous solutions is particularly complex because solute and water molecules themselves may exhibit varying affinities for water so that a stepwise increase in kinetic energy may cause the departure of water from one species and not another. This happens because of the formation of kinks¹.

Experimental

Distilled water (distilled once over potassium permanganate in all glass still), ethanol (purified by the reported method¹⁸), benzene and 1,4-dioxane (G.R., Qualinigns) were used. The purity of compounds was checked with an Abbe's type refractometer reading to 0.0002.

An all-glass electroosmotic transport cell used in the present investigation was similar to that described earlier⁹. A sintered glass membrane with porosity G 4 (Corning;

average pore radius 10 μm) was used which divided electroosmotic cell essentially into two compartments C (feed side; capacity 193 ± 0.5 ml) and D (permeate side; capacity 190 ± 0.5 ml). The procedure followed for the measurements was similar to that described earlier⁹.

It is worth to mention that two systems of liquid mixtures, namely, ethanol and benzene in which ethanol is more permeable, and water and dioxane in which water is more permeable, were chosen. Herein, we define former as system 1 and later as system 2. The following sets were planned to obtain data on electroosmosis.

System 1 :

- Set I : Both compartments C (feed side) and D (permeate side) were filled with ethanol.
- Set II : Both compartments were filled with benzene.
- Set III : Both compartments were filled with mixture of ethanol and benzene.
- Set IV : Compartment C was filled with mixture and D filled with benzene.
- Set V : Compartment C was filled with mixture and D was filled with ethanol.

System 2 :

- Set I : Both compartments C and D were filled with water.
- Set II : Both compartments C and D were filled with dioxane.
- Set III : Both compartments were filled with mixture of water and dioxane.
- Set IV : Compartment C was filled with mixture and D filled with dioxane.
- Set V : Compartment C was filled with mixture and D filled with water.

The maximum duration in each set of experiments never exceeded 4 h because during this time limit no attendant reduction in the concentration of solution on either side of the membrane was caused by adsorption at the septum. Also during this period the contribution of diffusion flux is very low in comparison to electroosmotic flux and quantitatively is too insignificant to be considered⁹. The experiments on electroosmosis were conducted while maintaining the condition of zero pressure difference across the membrane. After an interval of 30 min, in each

case, the feed and permeate solutions were analysed with the same refractometer. The composition of mixtures was generally 0.2 mole fraction of benzene (X_B) in system 1 and 0.1 mole fraction of dioxane (X_D) in system 2 in various sets unless otherwise stated.

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